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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF EFFECT OF EXTENSIVE SOCIAL MEDIA
USAGE ON MEDICAL STUDENT'S ACADEMIC
PERFORMANCE IN PAKISTAN**Ghulam Mustafa¹, Muhammad Jamil², Muhammad Amjad³¹Tehsil Headquarter Hospital Khairpur Tamewali, Bahawalpur²Civil Hospital Bahawalpur³District Headquarter Hospital Skardu**Abstract:**

Introduction: The social networking sites (SNSs) are dedicated websites or applications that allow the clients to communicate with each other for sharing information, posting videos, pictures, comments, and messages. **Aims and objectives:** The main objective of the study is to explore the impact of social media usage on the academic performance of medical students in the environment like Pakistan. **Methodology of the study:** This cross sectional study was conducted in medical colleges of Bahawalpur during 2018 to 2019. We have arranged a survey, in which we asked the respondents different questions regarding social networking sites and its upshots. Our targeted audience was medical students aged between 17-25 years. Our total answers were 100. A survey based approach was employed to investigate adoption of social media technologies and their impact on medical students' academic performance. **Results:** The data shows that there are number of factors which is attached with the use of social media and it directly effect on academic performance of medical students. They waste their money and time both on the use of different social media sites. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that social media play a negative role in the academic performance of medical students.

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INTRODUCTION:

The social networking sites (SNSs) are dedicated websites or applications that allow the clients to communicate with each other for sharing information, posting videos, pictures, comments, and messages¹. A wide range of media transmission devices are accessible for networking which are comprehensively characterized in six classifications, that is, web journals and microblogs (e.g., Twitter), synergistic undertakings (e.g., Wikipedia), content groups (e.g., YouTube), virtual social worlds (e.g., Second Life), virtual diversion worlds (e.g., World of Warcraft), and SNSs, for example, Facebook and MySpace. Google and Facebook are the most ordinarily utilized social media instruments, trailed by YouTube, Twitter, Flickr, and LinkedIn. The utilization of SNSs relies on particular necessities of the customers². Exactly, if an academician needs to administer students' utilization of social media, Facebook, the most prevalent SNS, would be a consistent decision. Then again, if a scientist or student wishes to take after discussions in a specific train or contribute by sharing novel research data, one may think about Twitter, a prominent microblogging SNS utilized by 15% of grown-ups. Blogging is prescribed for the individuals who wish to additionally build up their written work abilities. Commitment with social media can be close to home, proficient, or both, and there is adequate proof that carefully clever grown-ups and youth utilize social media for wellbeing related data³.

Social media utilizes versatile and electronic advancements to make exceptionally intelligent computerized stages through which people and groups share, co-make, talk about, and change their cooperation's. Points of interest of social media obviously incorporate quick and powerful correspondence among individuals, dynamic social and community oriented condition and helpful access to data and also advancing instrument for organizations⁴. Weaknesses of social media utilize, in any case, incorporate lessening of up close and personal communication among individuals, rest issues, tension and dejection, worries about protection, counterfeit character, time utilization and in particular dependence on social media that meddles with performing day by day assignments⁵. The quick headway of social media websites and applications together with the expanding prominence of social media among students have raised concerns in regards to the impact of these media on the scholarly execution of students. Significant worry for educators and guardians is the over the top time spent on facebook

and other social media to the detriment of finishing their scholarly undertakings. The consequences of the examinations on the impact of social media on understudy execution and grades have been negating⁶.

Social media is an idea in light of a stage for the general population around the globe to talk about their issues and assessments and trade data. What's more, social networking sites (SNS) are essentially those instruments that enables the general population to trade data, thoughts, pictures, recordings and substantially more through a particular system. Hardly any cases of SNS are Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Blizzard Entertainment, and WhatsApp and so on. SNS give its clients an office to make their own particular profile with their own rundown of clients⁷. With this rundown of clients, the individual can interface at that particular stage and that stage offers diverse highlights like visiting, blogging, sound and video calling, versatile network and video and photograph sharing.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to explore the impact of social media usage on the academic performance of medical students in the environment like Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross sectional study was conducted in medical colleges of Bahawalpur during 2018 to 2019. We have arranged a survey, in which we asked the respondents different questions regarding social networking sites and its upshots. Our targeted audience was medical students aged between 17-25 years. Our total answers were 100. A survey based approach was employed to investigate adoption of social media technologies and their impact on medical students' academic performance. The survey research is used to provide a quantitative description, explanation, or comparison of attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. After getting the data from survey, we statistically analyzed all the questions with respect to their variance, standard deviation, mean, standard error and satisfaction rate.

RESULTS:

Table 01 represents the data which shows that there are number of factors which is attached with the use of social media and it directly effect on academic performance of medical students. They waste their money and time both on the use of different social media sites.

Table 01: Factors affecting to the academic performance of student due to social media usage

Factors	Items	Mean	SD	Cronbach's alpha
Easy to use	4	3.70	0.677	0.819
Knowledge purpose	5	3.79	0.489	0.765
Behavior control	3	3.78	1.02	0.882
Attitude towards technology	4	3.77	0.897	0.675
Norms and values	3	3.03	1.01	0.987
Wastage of time	2	3.08	1.06	0.871
Wastage of money	2	3.63	1.03	0.925

Figure 1 shows that respondents' familiarity level with the use of social media technologies. Interestingly more than half of the respondents were having good familiarity level with the use of Facebook, YouTube and WhatsApp. The respondents were having poor knowledge and familiarity with the use of Twitter and Wikipedia. However, majority of the respondents were having average knowledge and familiarity in using Skype.

Figure 01: familiarity with the use of different social media sites

According to 70% of our respondents, SNS has a negative impact on their physical health. They think that once you get addicted to any social platform, then it will affect your time and physical health negatively. 30% said that it has a positive impact on their physical health. They think that if we use social platforms in a balanced way, then it will not affect your physical health negatively

DISCUSSION:

The social media has become one of the most vital communication means in recent years. In this examination setting, the outcomes uncover that separation training students utilize social media advancements and have great nature level with the utilization of the innovations like different students in formal instruction⁸. In like manner, social media advances turned out to be powerful methods for correspondence directs in advanced education. As discovered, remove instruction students utilize social media advances like Facebook, YouTube and WhatsApp and have great nature level with the utilization of the innovations. As dominant part of the respondents have commonality level with the advancements particularly Facebook, YouTube and WhatsApp which are generally utilized by the students, in this manner the students may not confront any troubles to utilize⁹.

Understanding the terms and strategies of any stage is especially vital. It can influence somebody's security and protection adversely. Thirdly, we arrived at the conclusion that social systems assumes a positive part in students' scholarly exercises¹⁰. Particularly utilizing Facebook, cohorts make a gathering and offer the addresses, introductions, assignments on that gathering. Amid exams, they share imperative inquiries and so forth it causes the entire class to know and to comprehend the issues or issues in detail. The following thing we found was that utilizing social stages for stimulation purposes negatively affects students' physical wellbeing. Those clients who plays internet amusements and the individuals who are someone who is addicted to any social stage turn out to be physically wiped out¹¹. Various types of side effects have been watched like unsteadiness, languor, a sleeping disorder, irritation and agony in the occipital bone of back. At times, they turn out to be so unsocial in their genuine lives that they disregard meeting vis-à-vis with their loved ones. We additionally became more acquainted with that extreme utilization of social stages or playing web based amusements for a more drawn out length

likewise influence your mental wellbeing contrarily¹²⁻¹³.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that social media play a negative role in the academic performance of medical students. At the end we will give certain suggestions to be followed to make the students' academic performance better. First thing we discovered was that in Pakistan, every student is using some kind of platform for socializing as well as for academic and educational purposes. Most of the students have accounts on Facebook and use YouTube for different purposes. If the students use these platforms in a balanced way, it will not harm their study and health

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